

Yield of wet season ratoon rice in Konkan region, Maharashtra, India

T. J. Varghese and B. P. Patil, Agricultural Research Station, Palghar, Maharashtra, India

About 9,000 ha of the rice area in Konkan are double-cropped, under irrigation Dec-May and rainfed Jun-Oct. The May harvest is just before the start of monsoon rains in June. This leaves little time for land preparation for the wet season (WS) rice crop.

A WS ratoon crop would eliminate labor and seed costs and free the farmer from conventional puddling and transplanting.

In 1990, we compared yields of a ratoon crop and a WS crop in 100-m² plots.

Promising, medium-long duration Palghar 103-1-2 (a derivative of IR5/Zinya 63) was transplanted in Dec and ratooned the third week of May by cutting 8-10 cm above the ground. The field was cleaned, immediately weeded, and irrigated. Fertilizer (50 kg N, 20 kg P, and 42 kg K/ha) was basally placed between rows. Another 25 kg N/ha was topdressed 30 d later, coinciding with the emergence of ratoon sprouts.

The regular WS crop of Palghar 103-1-2 was transplanted in an adjacent plot the first week of Jul 1990, using 30-d-old seedlings.

The rains started the first week of June. At 4 wk after main crop harvest, percent regenerated hills was 70.

Identical yield of the ratoon crop and the main WS crop can be attributed to the high number of basal tillers in the ratoon crop (see table). The ratio of basal tillers

Growth, yield attributes, and yield of ratoon rice and wet season rice.

Trait	Summer rice (Dee-May)	Ratoon rice ^a (Jun-Oct)	Wet season rice (Jun-Oct)
Plant height (cm)	103	133 55	135
Days to maturity	135	135 60	133
Panicle length (cm)	19	25 8	22
Number of spikelets/panicle	180	240 82	152
Productive tillers/hill	18	15 6	12
Grain yield (t/ha)	5.0	3.1	3.7

^aUpper figure is basal tillers, lower figure is ratoon sprouts.

to ratoon tillers was 2: 1. Favorable wet season conditions (high temperature and humidity) as well as physiologically active stubble may have contributed to the emergence of basal tillers. This is also a characteristic of Palghar 103-1-2. The basal tillers were superior to ratoon tillers in growth and yield attributes. ■

Pest resistance—diseases

Pathogenic races of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae*

S. Gopinathan, M. Gnanaguru, and M. V. Nayudu, Virology Department, S.V. University, Tirupati 517502, India

Bacterial blight (BB) caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (Xoo) is a major disease in India. We tested the pathogenicity of 12 of 37 isolates on 17 cultivars.

Rice seeds were treated with Dithane M 45 and germinated. Twenty-day-old

seedlings were transplanted in earthen pots at 5 seedlings/pot and fertilized.

At 35 d after transplanting, plants were inoculated with Xoo (0.2 O.D. concentration) by spraying the top 5 leaves. Disease symptoms were recorded beginning 8 d after inoculation as phase I = lesion desiccated and/or pale green, 0.3-3.0 cm long; phase II = lesion desiccated and/or pale green, 3.1-9.0 cm long; phase III = lesion pale green with yellow boundary along the margin, 9.1-25 cm long; phase IV = lesion with brown central zone surrounded by a pale green region and yellow boundary along the

margin, 25.1-40 cm long; and

phase V = lesion with central necrotic zone surrounded by a pale green region and yellow boundary along the margin, 40.1 cm long, or total leaf blight.

Lesions coalesce at different stages. Infection on any given day after inoculation was calculated:

$$\% \text{ infection} = \frac{\text{no. of lesions on all 5 leaves}}{5} \times 100$$

Most individual lesions had developed by phase II (see table). Later lesions coalesced, giving apparently less infection even though infection was severe.

All 12 isolates of Xoo were virulent on all 17 cultivars. Resistant varieties

Infection of 17 rice cultivars with 12 Xoo isolates.^a

Isolate ^b	Infection (%) 10-12 d after inoculation (phase II)																
	Rasi	LG (I)	LG (F)	MS	IR58	RE	Lorai	TN1	XM	WA	Jaya	HK	BJ (I)	BJ (T)	DV86	K	DV85
Xoo-2	72	64	68	64	56	64	60	64	60	44	56	40	56	60	52	56	64
Xoo-3	60	64	64	60	48	64	60	60	64	64	64	64	60	64	56	60	60
Xoo-12	64	60	64	60	60	60	64	64	64	60	60	56	56	60	64	60	56
Xoo-13	64	60	56	64	60	60	56	56	56	60	60	64	64	60	44	60	56
Xoo-16	60	60	56	60	64	56	64	60	56	54	64	60	56	64	50	64	60
Xoo-17	64	56	60	60	60	60	64	48	60	60	44	60	60	60	60	60	56
Xoo-21	72	60	60	60	52	64	64	60	60	64	60	60	56	60	68	40	60
Xoo-22	76	60	60	60	60	60	48	60	60	60	64	60	56	56	60	64	56
Xoo-26	76	60	60	60	60	68	60	60	56	64	44	60	60	60	60	60	64
Xoo-27	72	60	56	64	60	60	60	56	56	64	60	56	56	56	56	40	60
Xoo-36	72	52	60	60	56	68	64	60	60	64	64	52	52	60	60	60	56
Xoo-37	72	60	60	60	48	56	60	60	56	64	60	60	56	56	56	60	60

^a LG = Long pin, MS = Malagkit Sungsong, RE = Rantai Emas, RM = Rantai Mas, WA = Wase Aikoku 3, HK = Hashikalmi, I = India, F = Fiji, K = Kogyoku, T = Thailand. ^bAll isolates were derived from an Andhra isolate except 2 (Xoo-36 and Xoo-37) from Tamil Nadu.